

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Spain: An Introduction

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Responsibility Allocation System

State and autonomous region statutes confer powers to local entities in a wide range of matters. The Law of the Basis of the Local System (LBRL) ensures that these powers are related to a list of important action fields, such as urban planning, urban environment, water supply and sanitation services and collective transport, among others. In addition, this act sets up a limit to this allocation of powers: the possible duplication of responsibilities in different tiers of government (Article 25). Alongside this regulation, the LBRL (Article 26) requires municipalities to offer a list of services, which varies according to the number of inhabitants (less than 5,000, more than 20,000 and more than 50,000). In municipalities with less than 20,000 inhabitants, the provinces must coordinate the provision of some services, such as waste collection, water supply and sanitation services and street lighting. The number of inhabitants is an important difference that could be drawn between urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs), considering that RLGs in Spain are significantly smaller than ULGs.

Local governments have a limited influence on the design of this responsibility allocation system. Capital cities usually play an important role in the policy-making processes of other tiers of government. So does the Spanish Association of Municipalities and Provinces (*Federación Española de Municipios y Provincias*, FEMP), which is the only and most important association of its kind, representing both ULGs and RLGs. Statutes often provide for the participation of this Association in different decision-making processes.

Forms of Public Service Management and Delivery

The Local Government Act lists several forms of public service management and delivery (Article 85 LBRL). On the one hand, there are modalities of direct service delivery, in which services are provided by the local government itself or by an entity (of a public or private legal nature) fully owned by the municipality alone or together with other municipalities or local authorities (in 2018 there were 4,331 of these entities); on the other hand, local governments can enter into public contracts by awarding service contracts or concessions governed by the Public Contracts Act (2017) (hereinafter LCSP) – these are always characterized as indirect service delivery forms.

When regulating these mechanisms of public service management, the LBRL makes no distinction between ULGs and RLGs. But there are important differences in practice. RLGs are usually smaller than ULGs and have fewer human and material resources. Therefore, they are

less capable of delivering public services on their own. In these cases, inter-municipal cooperation plays a very important role and so does the assistance role of the provinces helping RLGs rendering services. In both scenarios it is possible to create an inter-municipal cooperation scheme (*mancomunidad*); and/or to set up a new body, like a public company (jointly controlled by different municipalities or controlled by the province). Nevertheless, RLGs tend to prefer the first option, entering into agreements to establish inter-municipal cooperation schemes aimed at providing particular public services (i.e., waste collection, water supply). As for the ULGs, it is important to highlight the wave of remunicipalization processes that took place during the economic crisis (for instance, water supply in the City of Valladolid). Distrust of private contractors prompted a process of contracting-in certain public services in some municipalities (usually with left-wing governments). However, many of these attempts were frustrated because of the high transition costs and the legal and economic difficulties.

With regard to indirect service delivery, ULGs and RLGs are subject to the same legal provisions established in the LCSP. Smaller RLGs tend to resort to the general assistance of the province, as well as to the provincial centralized purchasing systems and those of the Spanish Association of Municipalities and Provinces (*Federación Española de Municipios y Provincias*). By doing that, they somewhat lose control over the contract awarding procedure.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Cidoncha Martín A, 'La garantía constitucional de la autonomía local y las competencias locales: un balance de la jurisprudencia del Tribunal Constitucional' (2017) 45 Cuadernos de Derecho Local 12

Huergo Lora A, 'La prestación de los servicios públicos locales' (2019) 6 Documentación Administrativa. Nueva Época 129

López de Castro García-Morato L, 'Formas de gestión de los servicios públicos locales' in Francisco Velasco Caballero (ed), *Tratado de Derecho Económico Local* (Marcial Pons 2017)

Velasco Caballero F, 'Juicio constitucional sobre la LRSAL: punto final' (2016) 10 Anuario de Derecho Municipal 21

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